

Original Article

Sonographic Splenic Length and its Correlation with Biodata in Adult Nigerians in Oghara, South South Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

Awareness of the varying size of the spleen in different populations is crucial in the screening and diagnosis of splenic pathologies. This study aimed at determining the splenic length and its correlation with biodata variables of adult Nigerians in Oghara, Delta state of the south-south region of Nigeria. Five hundred and ninety-seven adult volunteers were randomly selected from the staff and students of a Teaching Hospital in Delta State, Nigeria, following institutional ethical approval. After obtaining informed consent from each participant, a brief history and physical examination was conducted, the age and sex recorded and the measurements of height and weight taken. Ultrasound scanning of the upper abdomen was conducted by a single investigator and the splenic length (in centimeters) was measured. Data obtained was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences Version 22.0 and summarized in means and standard deviations. The difference in the splenic length was probed using independent t test and analysis of variance in the different gender and age groups respectively. Pearson's correlation test was used to test for the association between the splenic length and the anthropometric variables. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. An average splenic length of 9.91 ± 1.56 cm was found with its significant positive correlation with height. This variable did not show any significant association with gender, age, weight and BMI. The findings of this study vary from previous Nigerian studies, therefore providing a splenic dataset specific for Delta State to enhance accurate diagnosis and screening for splenic pathologies in our population.

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INTRODUCTION

The spleen is the largest lymphoid organ located intraperitoneally in the left hypochondrium between the fundus of the stomach and the left hemidiaphragm.¹ In the supine position, the spleen is associated with the 9th to 11th ribs while its long axis is parallel to the 10th rib.^{2,3} The adult spleen averagely weighs 80-300g and measures 12cm long, 7cm broad and 3cm thick.⁴ Its white

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pulp contains lymphoid cells while the red pulp harbours mononuclear phagocytic macrophages that filter unwanted elements from the blood by phagocytosis.⁵ The spleen receives 5% of cardiac output and 40% of blood in the portal circulation. It serves as a blood reservoir in case of hemorrhagic shock.⁶ It also destroys worn out red blood cells and aids in the recycling of iron.⁷

A normal spleen is rarely palpable on the anterolateral body wall.² The size of the spleen serves as an indicator of the disorders of the gastrointestinal, hematological and reticuloendothelial systems since it is altered by infective, infiltrative, metabolic, hematopoietic, immunologic and malignant conditions.^{8,9} Splenic atrophy following vaso-occlusion and infarction may occur in sickle cell disease.¹ On the other hand, enlargement of the spleen (splenomegaly) can be moderate (11-20cm) or severe (>20cm).¹⁰ Splenomegaly may be due to infections such as malaria, Kalazar and infectious mononucleosis as well as hematological conditions like leukemia, lymphoma and myeloproliferative diseases.^{10,11} Conditions with portal hypertension such as liver cirrhosis may also present with an enlarged spleen. The spleen is also involved in amyloidosis, sarcoidosis, glycogen storage disorders, phosphorus and arsenic poisoning and congestive heart failure with ascites.^{12,13}

Physical examination by palpation may not accurately identify the early changes in the size of the spleen.^{3,9} Furthermore, a spleen must be 2-3 times enlarged before its anterior border extends beyond the left costal margin and becomes palpable.^{11,12} A non-palpable spleen may not be normal size while a normal spleen may be palpable in some cases.^{3,14} Ultrasonography adequately demonstrates the splenic echotexture, outline and presence of a mass. It is more accurate than clinical examination in early detection of mild enlargement of the spleen. Moreover, it is safe, painless, non-invasive, affordable, widely available, non-ionizing and

provides real-time images.^{3,12}

The size and dimensions of the spleen vary in different populations. The knowledge of population specific splenic data set provides more accurate standards to clinicians, surgeons and radiologists to aid in the appropriate diagnosis, management and follow-up of disorders involving the spleen.^{2,11,15} This study therefore aimed at determining the splenic length in apparently healthy Nigerian adults in Delta State Nigeria and also to establish its correlation with body weight, height, and Body Mass Index (BMI).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This cross-sectional study was conducted in the Radiology Department of the Delta State University Teaching Hospital (DELSUTH) Oghara, Delta State Nigeria within a span of 3 months (from December 2020 to March 2021). Approval was obtained from the Hospital's Research and Ethics committee prior to commencement of this study (Ref No: HERC/PAN/046/0387). The sample size was obtained based on the formula $[NS = N / (1 + (N(e)^2))]$ 16 where:

NS= Sample size

N= Estimated population size = 400000

e = chosen error margin at 95% confidence interval = 5%.

Therefore $NS = 400,000 / (1 + (400,000)(0.05)^2) = 399$

However, 597 subjects were recruited so as to increase the statistical power of the study. Using simple random sampling technique, 597 apparently healthy adult volunteers aged 18 years and above were recruited from the hospital staff as well as medical and nursing students of the institution. These subjects were informed about the study and they gave their informed written consent. Following a brief clinical history and physical examination, subjects with recent history of malaria, typhoid fever, prolonged febrile illness or fever at the time of examination were excluded. Subjects with history of

splenectomy or hematological diseases such as sickle cell were not included in this study. Additionally, adults with chronic diseases such as chronic liver or kidney disease, malignancies as well as pregnant females were excluded from the study. Subjects with clinical or sonographic evidence of splenic parenchymal mass lesions, abnormal echotexture of the spleen, accessory spleen and cysts were also excluded from the study.

The demographic data (age and sex) of the participants were documented. Using a stadiometer, the height of the subjects was measured in meters. A weighing scale (Marsden ocean scale) calibrated in kilograms was used to measure their weights. After explaining the procedure, the subjects were requested to lie supine on the examination couch, with the abdominal wall relaxed, and arms positioned parallel to the body. The abdomen was adequately exposed by the patient, from the xiphisternum to the pubic symphysis and acoustic coupling gel was applied over the abdomen. Scanning was done using a Sonoline G50 ultrasound scan machine (Siemens medical solutions USA, 2005) that is coupled with a 2.5-5.5 MHz curvilinear transducer placed in the left upper quadrant along the left costal margin. Scanning was done in supine and right lateral decubitus positions. Additionally, scanning on deep inspiration was done so that the spleen could descend for better visualization. Where the lung base obscured the spleen in deep inspiration, the scans were obtained at rest or on shallow inspiration.

The spleen with its homogenous echogenicity was visualized in the left upper quadrant and seen to be related to the left kidney (Figure 1). The splenic length was measured as the maximum distance between the dome of the spleen and splenic tip on the longitudinal section in centimeters.9 (Figure 1). To avoid inter-observer errors, all the abdominal ultrasound scans were undertaken by a senior resident doctor of Radiology department with six years' experience in sonography. Furthermore, to

minimize intra-observer errors, the splenic dimensions were measured three times and the mean values recorded

Figure 1: Longitudinal sonogram of the left upper abdomen showing the spleen which is related to the left kidney. The splenic length is measured as the maximum distance between the dome of the spleen and splenic tip (A-B).

The data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences for Windows version 22.0 (SPSS Inc. Chicago, IL, USA). The subjects were classified according to gender and in 10-year age-groups. The body mass index was calculated as a ratio of weight in Kg to height in squared metres. Based on the BMI, subjects were classified as underweight ($<15.5 \text{ Kg/m}^2$), normal ($18.5\text{-}24.99 \text{ kg/m}^2$), overweight ($25\text{-}30 \text{ m}^2$) and obese ($>30 \text{ kg/m}^2$). The data were summarized in means and standards deviation. Splenomegaly was defined by splenic length that measured more than 12cm. Independent t test was used to test for gender difference in the length of the spleen and the biodata variables. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to probe for any significant difference between the splenic length in the various age and BMI groups. Using Pearson's correlation test, the splenic length was correlated with the age, gender, weight, height, and body mass index. P-value of

<0.05 was considered statistically significant at 95% confidence interval.

RESULTS

This study recruited 597 apparently healthy adults comprising of 294 males (49.2%) and 303 females (50.8%). Table 1 illustrates the age distribution and mean splenic length for each age group of the study participants. Majority of the participants were in the 30-39 year age group (130, 21.8%) followed by the 40-49 years (115, 19.3%) age-groups (Table 1). The youngest subjects (20-29 years and 30-39 years) had the smallest spleens while the longest spleen length was observed in the 50-59 years' age-group, followed by 40-49 years and 60-69 years' age groups (Table 1). The differences of the splenic length in the different age-groups was not statistically significant ($p=0.239$) (Table 1). Splenomegaly ($SL>2\text{cm}$) was observed in 74 patients (12.4%).

Table 1: Age distribution and mean splenic length for each age group of the study participants

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean splenic length (cm)	P-value
20-29	63	10.6	9.47	0.239
30-39	130	21.8	9.79	
40-49	115	19.3	10.03	
50-59	106	17.8	10.05	
60-69	101	16.9	10.03	
70-79	64	10.7	9.57	
≥ 80	18	3.0	9.89	

Table 2 shows the comparison of mean values of the study parameter for the male and female participants. The age range of the participants was 20-93 years with a mean age of 49.29 ± 16.46 years. The mean weight and height was 74.76 ± 12.38 Kg and $1.69\pm 0.08\text{m}$ respectively. The average BMI was $26.0\pm 3.73\text{Kg/m}^2$ (Table 2). The average weight and height in males was significantly higher than in females ($P<0.05$). The length of the spleen ranged from 5.9cm to 13.1cm with an average of $9.91\pm 1.56\text{cm}$ (Table 2). It was longer in females than

in males, however, the difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.660$) (Table 2). There was no significant gender difference in age and BMI ($P=0.431, 0.757$) (Table 2). The height and BMI showed a significant association with the age-groups ($p=0.001, 0.007$)

Table 2: Comparison of mean values of the study parameter for males and females

Parameter		Mean		P-value
		Males	Females	
Age (Years)	49.29 ± 16.46	49.24	49.34	0.431
Weight (Kg)	74.76 ± 12.38	75.83	73.73	0.038
Height (m)	1.69 ± 0.08	1.7	1.68	0.002
BMI (Kg/m^2)	26.00 ± 3.73	26.05	25.96	0.757
Splenic length(cm)	9.91 ± 1.56	9.88	9.94	0.660

The categories based on the Body Mass Index (BMI) of the study participants are displayed in Figure 2. Normal BMI was recorded in only 208 subjects (34.8%). Majority of the participants were overweight (324, 54.3%) while 55, 9.2% were obese. We report a low prevalence of underweight (6, 1.0%) and morbidly obese subjects (4, 0.7%)

Figure 2: Distribution of Body Mass Index (BMI) in percentages

The mean splenic length was lowest in underweight individuals at 9.33cm and was highest in morbidly overweight respondents at 10.08cm. Individuals with normal BMI had a mean splenic length of 9.76cm.

Figure 3: Bar chart showing the mean splenic length for each BMI group of the participants.

The splenic length showed a weak positive correlation with age, weight, BMI and height ($0 < r < 0.5$) as depicted in Table 3. The correlation of splenic length with height was statistically significant ($p=0.033$)

Table 3: Correlation between splenic length and the biodata variables

Variables	Pearson Coefficient (r)	Correlation P-value
Age	0.077	0.060
Weight	0.019	0.636
Height	0.087	0.033
BMI	0.013	0.760

DISCUSSION

The mean length of the spleen in our study (9.91cm) was lower than the findings of Demissie *et al*,¹ Yahuza *et al*,⁹ Badran *et al*,¹⁰ and Chow *et al*,¹⁷ in Ethiopia, Nigeria (Kano), Jordan and Germany respectively. This length was higher than the findings from studies which included younger subjects such as Uduoka *et al*,¹⁸ who recruited 18-40-year-old subjects and Kanakaraj and Mariappan,¹² who included subjects less than 18 years. The length was also higher than the reports by Yousef,⁸ Sharma and Gupta¹⁵ and Gangte *et al*.³ in Sudan and India respectively. The discrepancies in the SL in literature have been ascribed to differences in genetics, race, age, sex, body constitution, geographical condition, feeding habits, nutritional status, body conditions, better socioeconomic status in the western countries and endemicity of sickle cell disease and malaria.^{4,13,14} Other factors that contribute to this variation include the differences in the sample size, sample composition (age and sex distribution) and anthropometric measurements of subjects used in different studies.^{1,11}

Congruent with the reports of Yahuza *et al*,⁹ the SL did not show any significant association with gender. On the contrary, Ehimwenma and Tagbo² reported significantly larger splenic length in males than their female counterparts in Benin South-South Nigeria. This variation could be due to the differences in sample size and sample composition. A significant gender difference was also observed in Korea and Ethiopia perhaps suggesting ethnic and genetic variation.^{1,19} It has previously been postulated that males have longer splenic lengths than females due to the differences in genetics that influence the variation in weight, height, body surface area and development of organs.^{14,15,20} Conversely, females have smaller spleens due to a lower total red cell mass compared to males.¹⁷

The smallest SL was observed in the youngest age-

group (20-29 years) while the 50-59 years' age-group had the largest splenic length. This was contrary to Chime *et al.*,²¹ in Enugu Nigeria who reported longest SL in the youngest group (30-39 years) and smallest SL in the 50-59 years age-group. In Ethiopia, the highest SL was observed in the 31-40 years age group while lowest SL was documented in subjects above 50 years.¹ Sharma and Gupta,¹⁵ reported a significant decrease in the SL after the age of 50 years. According to Yahuza *et al.*,⁹ the smaller SL in the older subjects is attributed to the reduction in the size of mass organs with age. Furthermore, aging is associated with a decrease in the size of B cell follicles in the white pulp and reduction in size of the germinal center.¹ Consistent with the findings of Chime *et al.*,²¹ the variations of the splenic lengths in the different age-groups was not statistically significant herein. On the contrary, among the Indians studied by Sharma and Gupta,¹⁵ a significant difference between the 10-year age-groups was observed.

We observed a weak positive correlation between the SL and age and this corresponded with the findings of Yahuza *et al.*,⁹ and contrasted with the negative correlation documented by Chime *et al.*²¹ and Uduoka *et al.*,¹⁸ in Nigeria as well as Yousef,⁸ in Sudan. Congruent with these scholars, the correlation between the SL with age was not statistically significant. On the other hand, Gangte *et al.*³ in India documented a significant decrease in the SL with age. The splenic length showed a weak positive correlation with height and this was akin to the reports by Uduoka *et al.*,¹⁸ and Yahuza *et al.*,⁹ in Kano State, Nigeria, observed a strong positive correlation between these variables. According to these scholars, the growth of an individual causes an increase in the size of the spleen, with very tall individuals (6 feet) having larger spleen sizes (>13cm). The significant increase in SL with height in this study corresponded with the findings of Yousef,⁸ and Demissie *et al.*¹

Similar to the findings by Ehimwenma and Tagbo,² we observed a weak positive correlation between SL and weight. Conflicting with the findings of Yousef,⁸ Gul *et al.*,²² Kim¹⁹ and Demissie *et al.*,¹ the positive correlation herein was not statistically significant. The SL and weight showed a strong positive and weak negative association among the Nigerians studied by Yahuza *et al.*,⁹ and Uduoka *et al.*¹⁸ correspondingly. According to Chow *et al.*,¹⁷ the spleen size increases with an increase in body weight. Findings in our study showed overweight and obese subjects having larger mean splenic length when compared to normal subjects but, showed a weak positive correlation between SL and BMI, this however, was not statistically significant. Chow *et al.*¹⁷ also documented a positive correlation with overweight and obese subjects having larger spleens compared to subjects with normal BMI. On the contrary, Uduoka *et al.*,¹⁸ reported a weak negative correlation between SL and BMI in southern Nigeria. Consistent with our findings, Ehimwenma and Tagbo,² did not observe any significant correlation between these variables in Benin, Nigeria. According to Badran *et al.*,¹⁰ Yousef,⁸ and Demissie *et al.*,¹ an increase in height, weight and BMI is associated with larger blood volume hence requiring a larger spleen for effective blood filtration. Nonetheless, this may not be the case in the study population herein. The correlation between the SL and the anthropometric variables vary in different populations. This is perhaps due to the differences in the sample sizes, sample composition (gender and age-group distribution), genetics, nutritional status, physical activity, ethnicity, and body habitus.

Splenomegaly was observed in 12.4% of the study population. On the contrary, Chime *et al.*,²¹ did not observe any splenomegaly among the adult Nigerians they evaluated in Enugu. This variation is due to the different definition used for splenomegaly. Our study used a lower splenic length cutoff (12cm) while Chime *et al.*,²¹ defined splenomegaly based on the splenic length of more than 13 cm.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study have provided splenic dataset to enhance the accuracy in diagnosis of splenic pathologies and have increased the reliability of using sonographic splenic length in screening of patients with splenic malady in Delta State Nigeria.

Recommendation

Due to the existence of anthropological variation, studies among different ethnic groups and geographical locations of the country should be carried out and nomograms designed. This will provide a splenic dataset for various ethnic groups while enhancing the accuracy in the diagnosis of splenic pathologies.

Limitation

The restriction of this study to only the south-south region of Nigeria constitutes a limitation of the study.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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